

A general philosophical analysis of engineering

1. **Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich.** Professor of Tashkent State Transport University.
2. **Hamidjonov Islomjon Ibrohim o‘g‘li.** Student of Tashkent State Transport University.

Abstract. The term "engineer" is derived from the Latin language and means "ingenious, inventor". Initially, engineers were called people who drive military vehicles. With the appearance of the word "machine" in the ancient Greek theater, which means a lifting device, the creators of all kinds of ingenious technical tools began to be called engineers.

Key words: engineer, engineer, machine, ability, reliability, economy, welfare.

The term "engineer" is derived from the Latin language and means "ingenious, inventor". Initially, engineers were called people who drive military vehicles. With the appearance of the word "machine" in the ancient Greek theater, which means a lifting device, the creators of all kinds of ingenious technical devices began to be called engineers. In the 16th century in Holland, the concept of "civil engineer" appeared in relation to bridge and road builders. Then this concept is used in England and other European countries.

<http://innconferences.iblogger.org/>

The concept and title of engineer has long been used in Russia, where engineering education was founded in 1701. A school of mathematics and navigational sciences was opened in Moscow, and then in 1712 the first engineering school was opened. Engineers worked in the Russian army of the 16th century. The word "engineer" in the modern sense began to be used in connection with the emergence of large-scale machine production in the 18th century. It was during this period that a whole system of special technical sciences designed to combine scientific knowledge with practice was formed.

An engineer is a specialist who carries out technical creativity in a professional manner, has a higher technical education, connects science with production in his work, and has become a conductor of science in production.

Engineering activity is a professional technical activity of a person (with higher technical education) and is a means of his livelihood. With the complexity of production processes, engineering activities were divided into engineering research, engineering design, and engineering and technology.

In contrast to the activities of other layers of intellectuals (teachers, doctors, actors, composers, etc.), the work of an engineer is an effective labor that directly participates in the creation of national income in terms of its role in social production. Thus, engineers perform one of the isolated functions of a general worker. The practical direction of engineering and, in general, all technical activities caused the "intellectuals" to look down on it. In its modern essence, engineering activity is the technical application of science aimed at the production of technology and the satisfaction of social and technical

<http://innoconferences.iblogger.org/>

needs. In the course of the engineer's work, the laws of science turn from their theoretical form into technical principles that find practical application. It is considered inevitable that this activity has a certain level of risk. In order to ensure the necessary reliability of the created technical means and technologies, methods and means of eliminating this risk are being created by establishing certain parameters, standards and using statistical records of possible accidents. By its nature, engineering activity is primarily a spiritual activity in the field of material production. In its time, the German Engineers Union defined the main value criteria for engineering activities, which are: performance and reliability, economy, welfare, health, safety, environmental cleanliness, quality of society and personal development. The process of engineering activities includes: identification of needs, development and decision-making, preparation of production, regulation of production, satisfaction of needs. The important features of engineering activities are as follows:

- 1) it is an activity in the field of material production or an activity aimed at solving material production problems;
- 2) this activity is practical and deals with real-life objects, as opposed to theoretical or spiritual, where there are ideal objects that can be imagined;
- 3) this activity resolves the conflicts between the object (nature) and the subject (society), it is the process of turning the natural into the social and the natural into the artificial;

4) this activity occupies an intermediate position between theory and practice (engineer work is mental work in the field of material production).

Thus, engineering activity is the implementation of a technical idea that ends with the creation of an efficient industrial object, the analysis of its operation affects the engineering thinking, as well as the development of technical science and science in general.

The following stages of the development of engineering activities can be distinguished:

1) pre-engineering - the time of construction of large and complex structures of antiquity;

2) pre-engineering period - the period of production, the stage of formation of engineering activity from a social point of view (end of the 18th - beginning of the 19th century);

3) the period of development of engineering activities based on the system of engineering and technical sciences;

4) the modern stage associated with the transition to information technologies.

Technical activity did not gain special fame even in ancient times. Criticism of technical activity turns out to be as old as the activity itself (the myth of the destruction of the Tower of Babel by God; the myth of Prometheus chained to the rocks of the Caucasus; the myth of Icarus falling from the sky). Archimedes considered the construction of machines to be a

<http://innconferences.iblogger.org/>

profession not worthy of labor and attention (most of them appeared in the world, as if in the form of entertainment). Although the attitude towards technical activity was often perceived as something magical in the Middle Ages, this activity did not change fundamentally. In the Middle Ages, crafts were likened to a ritual that repeated the relevant myth, and in Europe, technical innovations, styles and methods were incorporated into the classroom world of workshops. During the renaissance, a different attitude towards the engineer and his work was formed. The engineer began to be treated not just as a craftsman, a technician, but as a creator who creates a new world, a second natural world, like a divine creator.

From the end of the 19th century, a sharp criticism of technical superiority and idealization of the past begins. Modern society also has a very opposite assessment of engineering activity, which is not only a source of life benefits, but also a social evil. However, only in the 20th century did the development of technology, its place in society and its importance for the future of human civilization become the subject of systematic study. Not only philosophers, but also engineers began to pay more attention to the understanding of technology. In particular, this topic was hotly discussed in the pages of the "Technology and Culture" magazine of the Union of German Chartered Engineers in the 1930s. It can be said that during this period, the need for a philosophical understanding of the technical phenomenon and one's own activities for its creation increases in the engineering environment itself. Often, attempts at such an understanding have been reduced to only an optimistic assessment of the achievements and prospects of modern

technical development. At the same time, in the humanitarian environment, the critical attitude towards the technological development of the modern society increased, and attention was firstly paid to its negative aspects. In any case, in both cases, the technique became the subject of special analysis and research.

REFERENCES

1. Salimov B. L. (2023). TEXNIKA TARAQQIYOTI BORASIDAGI FALSAFIY KONSEPSIYALAR. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3 (11), 333-337.
2. Salimov B. L., Erkinov S. T., Maxammatova M. X. (2023). TEXNIKA VA TEXNOSFERA TUSHUNCHALARINING FALSAFIY MOHIYATI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3 (11), 324-328.
3. Baxriddin Lutfullaevich Salimov, Shoxrux Quranboevich Otaxonov. [THE ROLE OF NANOTECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY](#). Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal. 2023. №1/8. 136-141.
4. Baxriddin Lutfullaevich Salimov, Bekzod Zokirovich Sarsenboev. [DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNICAL SYSTEMS AND ENGINEERING THINKING](#). Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal. 2023. №1/8. 80-85.
5. Baxriddin Lutfullaevich Salimov, Aziza Xajamberdievna Bektasheva. [THE ROLE OF VALUE RELATIONSHIPS IN THE FORMATION OF ENGINEERING PHILOSOPHY](#). Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal. 2023. №1/8. 166-172.

<http://innconferences.iblogger.org/>

6. Baxriddin Lutfullaevich Salimov, Damir Abduvalievich Rahimov. [REPRESENTATION OF HUMAN ACTIVITY IN TECHNICAL NATURE.](#) Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal. 2023. №1/8. 91-97.
7. Baxriddin Lutfullaevich Salimov, Muhammaddiyor Oybekovich Abdukhalikov. [DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIONS AND TRANSPORT IN UZBEKISTAN OVER THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE.](#) ILM FAN TARAQQIYOTIDA ZAMONAVIY METODLARNING QO'LLANILISHI. 2023. №3/31. 76-80.
8. Baxriddin Lutfullaevich Salimov, Quvonchbek Turg'unovich Normamatov. [TECHNICAL PHILOSOPHY AS A PART OF THE HISTORY OF HUMAN DEVELOPMENT.](#) Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal. 2023. №1/8. 98-103.
9. Baxriddin Lutfullaevich Salimov, Zainiddin Elmuratovich Jurakulov. [MODERN MECHANICAL ENGINEERING AND NANOTECHNOLOGIES.](#) Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal. 2023. №1/8. 159-165.
10. Baxriddin Lutfullaevich Salimov, Dmitriy Vladimirovich Shushakov. [STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE.](#) Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal. 2023. №1/8. 126-131.
11. Baxriddin Lutfullaevich Salimov, Yevgeniy Viktorovich Remenyuk. [PHILOSOPHICAL FEATURES OF TECHNICAL EXISTENCE.](#) Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal. 2023. №1/8. 173-178.
12. Baxriddin Lutfullaevich Salimov, Arslonbek Axmedovich Ruzmetov. [VIEWS OF M. HEIDEGGER AND K. JASPERS ON TECHNOLOGY AND PHILOSOPHY OF TECHNOLOGY.](#) Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal. 2023. №1/8. 187-192.

<http://innoconferences.iblogger.org/>

13. Baxriddin Lutfullaevich Salimov, Hojiakbar Olimjonovich Odilov. [SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL IMPACT OF ENGINEERING THINKING](#). Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal. 2023. №1/8. 142-146.
14. Baxriddin Lutfullaevich Salimov, Davlet Rashidovich Gaipov. [IMPORTANT PROBLEMS OF TECHNICAL PHILOSOPHY](#). Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal. 2023. №1/8. 152-158.
15. Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг шаклланиши ва барқарорлигини белгиловчи муҳим тамойиллар. Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. 3(3), March, 2023.
16. Salimov, B., Madalimov, T. (2023). Transport falsafasi. Globe Edit.
17. Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.
18. Bakhridin Lutfullaevich Salimov. NEGATIVE CONSEQUENCES OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT. International Conference" Law, Economics and Tourism sciences in the modern world". 2023/5/1. С. 5-10.